
**PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL
EDUCATION AND MASS SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN.**

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Annotation.

This article describes physical education and sports as factors that play a very important role in the development of society. Meanwhile, in the author's opinion, there is a situation all over the world that leads to a decrease in the physical culture and wellness activity of people, a deterioration in health and a decrease in labor productivity. The author argues that by increasing investment in mass sports, it is possible to increase the labor productivity of the economically active population. The article presents empirical and experimental data confirming a decrease in morbidity, an increase in the useful fund of working time, an increase in the speed of performing mental and physical labor and an increase in labor productivity. Investments in physical education and Sports will reduce the state's spending on medical services and increase a person's working age, which in turn will reduce pension costs. This article also reveals the problem of the impact of investments in physical education on increasing labor productivity.

Keywords.

investments, mass sports, labor productivity, working age, cost reduction, medical provision of citizens, payment of pensions.

In the past hundred years in our country, physical education and sports have played a very important role in the development of society. Physical culture is an activity aimed at the development of physical health, part of a general culture, which includes sports skills, scientific knowledge in this area. An important motive that motivates a person to play sports is the pursuit of not only physical perfection (body beauty), but also spiritual perfection, which allows you to use physical health in the interests of society in accordance with its needs. In ancient times, a person had the incredible power necessary to protect himself from wild animals and preserve his family. Russian scientist M.M. Gerasimov examined the remains of an ancient man (20 thousand years) found on the territory of the Vladimir region. The width of the shoulders was 60 cm, and the height was more than 180 cm. Myths

and epics from the later period of human development brought us the courage of Ilya Muromets, Alyosha Popovich, Dobrynya Nikitich and other Russian heroes. To have agility of movement and achieve physical perfection, people used different games. Until now, people knew games like rounders, suburbs. In some periods, the development of physical education was hindered by the authorities themselves. For example, in ancient times, by decree of kings, nobles were forbidden to engage in any game. Glorious pages of victories at international competitions and Olympic Games brought glory to the homeland of Uzbekistan and preserved the high reputation of the motherland in the field of foreign policy. In the 90s, physical education in Uzbekistan began to decline. Sports societies and organizations began to move to a commercial basis. The attitude of young people to Sports has not changed for the better. Due to the large number of Westerners, the characters turned out to be "tough guys" with guns in their hands, cigarettes in their mouths. The promotion of a lifestyle with the slogan "Take everything from life" had severe social consequences. Addiction, alcoholism, nicotine addiction began to develop. Scientists said that the number of drug users is gradually decreasing. According to our estimates, the number of drug users is gradually decreasing: if a year or two ago the number of regular or occasional drug users was 8 million people, today their number has reached 7.3 million. The number of smokers is decreasing due to the fact that Uzbekistan promotes a healthy lifestyle, but the number is still very large. They showed that "during the year, the number of smokers in the country practically did not change - it still accounts for a third of Russians (35% in 2014 and 34% in 2015)". Against this background, fertility began to decrease and mortality began to increase (Figure 1, birth curve Blue Line, death curve red line). In 2014-2015, the number of births exceeded the number of deaths for the first time. Migration has become an important factor in population growth. According to statisticians, 857,654 Ukrainians and 127,264 Belarusians immigrated to Uzbekistan in 2014. The population began to increase (Figure 1, population curve is green). Currently, there is a situation around the world in which people's Physical Culture and wellness activity have decreased after 25 years. And this can lead to a decrease in his physical abilities during the most productive period of labor activity and, as a result, to a deterioration in health and a decrease in labor productivity. In Uzbekistan, a decrease in the effectiveness of sports and entertainment activities and a decrease in the financing of mass sports are manifested in the social parameters of life. Until now, the negative heritage of those years has been reflected in the health and mental state of citizens. In 2007, the negative trend began to gradually change to the positive. Physical education and sports became

fashionable, young people felt the need to play sports to ensure their competitiveness. Currently, the volume of paid services provided by sports organizations is increasing and the number of sports facilities is increasing (Table 1).

Name 2007 2011 2015

The total number of people involved in sports (weight %) in the population is
11 18 23

Number of sports facilities (presentation in units) 352 403 423

Paid services volume 10900 17000 25000

At the same time, it should be noted that today only 15% of the population of Uzbekistan is regularly engaged in sports. For comparison, let's take two states: 40% of the US, whose inhabitants regularly play sports, and 60% of the population in Germany. Despite the quantitative material changes taking place in the sports industry, the effectiveness of the complex of physical education and sports-wellness is, in general, not at a high level. This is also determined by the fact that the conscious orientation of financial resources on the physical health of the citizens of the country must be methodically ensured. The state or entrepreneur must ensure the quantitative dependence of the result of increasing labor productivity from the orientation of financial resources to physical education and mass sports. In other words, it is necessary to determine the economic effectiveness of promoting a healthy lifestyle in our country, investing in physical education and mass sports. Many countries are engaged in such studies to determine the age at which a person's mental and physical activity decreases. In addition, scientific work is being carried out on the extension of the active age of men and women. The purpose of the study is to increase the labor productivity of the active working population by increasing the energy capabilities of a person and prolonging the retirement age. It can be seen that the impact of physical health on the effectiveness and intensity of mental and physical labor is indisputable, but the limited possibilities of assessing the profitability of investments hinder this process. Physical education and sports have been proven to help increase the body's resistance to various diseases. Many empirical and experimental data confirm a decrease in morbidity, an increase in the useful fund of working time (extensive factor), an increase in the speed of performing mental and physical labor (intensive factor) and an increase in its productivity. . In addition, investments in physical education and Sports will reduce the state's spending on medical services and Pensions. Thus, the index of funds invested in physical education and Sports will depend on the influence of extensional factors and intensive factors.

$$I = (E_i + E_r) : I_0,$$

I-investment efficiency index;

I₀-initial investments;

EU, land-the effect of increasing labor productivity of intensive factors and extensive factors, respectively (saving from the influence of these factors affecting labor productivity).

In the process of calculating the effect of increasing labor productivity, it is necessary to take into account the share of each factor in the total volume of intensive and extensive factors. You should also pay attention to the possibility of the occurrence of the phenomenon from these factors. In conducting research, the famous economist E. Denison's works and analytical calculations should be used. E. Denison divided national income into two components: labor and capital, studying economic growth statistics. His early work was devoted to the study of the Cobb-Douglas production function, which, as you know, was used by scientists to assess the physical contribution of Labor and capital to the national product. These studies were conducted to determine growth factors.

According to the estimates of the United Nations, the population of Uzbekistan will be reduced, but the number of economically active residents of Uzbekistan, which will provide a labor supply in the labor market for the production of goods, the performance and provision of work. services are further reduced (birth rates have been declining in recent decades). Considering the decreasing birth rate in recent years, the increasing unemployment, it can be concluded that the country's gross domestic product is declining even with the same level of labor productivity preserved. The various scenarios of its decline are determined by the scenario of a decrease in the economically active population and unemployment. Thus, the investment aimed at the development of physical education and sports is one of the important directions for increasing labor productivity, increasing gross domestic product, strengthening public health and freeing up additional resources.

Projected population

Forecast values for the United Nations Population in Uzbekistan were used to construct the graph. The appearance of this graph is alarming, since the population of Uzbekistan (High curve) is decreasing and does not even remain at the level of 2015, even if the growth trend of childbirth continues. This leads to a negative trend of a decrease in gross domestic product, provided that the same value of labor productivity is maintained.

The problem of over-centralization and misuse of funds has existed in Uzbekistan for more than a year. This problem arises from the system of Public Administration, which is carried out through the subsystem of sports committees and departments of the federal agency for physical education and sports. Their activities are financed by the state budget and the income of their affiliated organizations and enterprises. The abundance of funding sources and levels of management leads to an incompatibility of the goals and interests of the participants. The same problems apply, but at a lower level, to sports teams run by trade unions and community organizations. They are funded at the expense of raising funds from the ministry, trade unions and, in part, the population. To solve their pressing problems, these organizations must first of all seek additional financial resources. Often, the benefits of physical education and sports organizations in the USSR were not the main goal of the organization's activities. Today, in conditions of crisis, sports and Recreation institutions, professional organizations depend on other sources of financing and, above all, on commercial activities, their sponsors. Therefore, whoever pays will order the music. Especially negative and corrupt phenomena occurring in the field of sports and sports organizations are affecting the organization of international competitions and the training of new professional athletes.

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